

Investigation of Effects of Pongamia Methyl Esters as A Green Fuel for Diesel Engine

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Abstract— There has been an apparent increase in the search for green fuels like biodiesel in recent years. The pressing need to contest climate change, minimize emissions of greenhouse gases, and discover renewable alternatives for current fossil fuels is an important factor in this research. A renewable energy source, biodiesel is made from organic ingredients like vegetable or animal fats and used cooking oils. Most studies show that biodiesel performs better than diesel in terms of efficiency. Engine tests were carried out to measure the performance and emission properties of the brakes, such as their thermal efficiency, their specific fuel consumption, their NO_x, smoke opacity, CO, and CO₂ emissions, and unburned hydrocarbons to evaluate and compute the diesel engines behavior powered by Pongamia methyl ester and its derivatives with diesel. In comparison to diesel fuel and other blended fuels, the results reveal that the Break Thermal Efficiency of the engine is about 30%, which is around 2% more than diesel with M20 fuel. Pure biodiesel has a greater BSFC than diesel fuels, while M20 fuel has a lower BSFC than diesel fuels and various blends. NO_x emissions are higher for pure biodiesel and lower for M20 fuel. Biodiesel and its blends greatly reduce hydrocarbon, CO, and smoke opacity. When compared to all blends, 20 percent Pongamia methyl esters with diesel fuel have higher performance and lower emission characteristics, according to engine performance and emission

Keywords— Diesel Engine; Pongamia Biodiesel; Performance; Exhausts Emissions; Efficiency

I. INTRODUCTION

For surface transportation, agricultural machinery, and other applications, the diesel engine is a popular prime mover and industrial. Almost 8.5 million engines are employed in India and the agriculture industry for a variety of applications. Imports of petroleum products are tremendously depleting our overseas reserves. The situation is only going to get worse in the coming years as demand rises. The major sources of carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, and unburned hydrocarbon emissions are gasoline and diesel engines, and a rise in carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide levels in the atmosphere causes global warming and the greenhouse effect. Swarup Kumar Nayak et al. [1] investigated the process of making biodiesel from plain Mahua oil using base-catalyzed transesterification and combining it with an appropriate additive (Dimethyl carbonate) in different volume ratios to create a fuel for engines. To evaluate the engine and output and emissions profile, the produced test fuels were tested under a variety of load circumstances on a diesel engine. The investigation and findings indicate that for all prepared test fuels, braking power and thermal efficiency rise with load S.K. Godiganur et. Al [2] studied how Karanja oil methyl ester affected diesel engines. The goal of this study was to assess the potential of Karanja oil methyl ester and its volumetric mix with diesel at concentrations ranging from 20% to 80%. According to the testing findings, the engine power of the combination is comparable to values produced from diesel fuel, and its exhaust emission levels are lower. The paper presents and discusses the utilization of waste plastic oil blended with fish biodiesel [3]. A Comparative Study of Ethanol and Methanol Addition Effects on Engine Performance Numerous tests were performed on a 10 HP single cylinder, 4 strokes, direct injection, and water-cooled diesel engine [11,13]. The load is progressively changed from 0-100 percent while the engine is designed to run at 1500 rpm. When compared to diesel, the break thermal Efficiency of biodiesel blends and biodiesel blends containing plastic oil rose by 3.82 percent and 10.02 percent, respectively. Vegetable oils are gaining popularity as an alternative fuel for diesel engines; according to Ramesha D. K. et al. Vegetable oils are transesterified to create esters, which lessens their high viscosity and low volatility. The performance, emissions, and behavior of diesel engines operating on the fuels were all computed through engine testing. Results indicate that Mahua methyl ester blend (B-20) works effectively when used at

200bar injection pressure, which is greater than the 180bar recommended injection pressure for diesel engines [4]. Naveen Kumar has presented that there would be plenty of opportunities to switch to locally produced, environmentally friendly biodiesel if erosion control and oil production were combined. India would gain from the biodiesel revolution since it would cost less to import oil. There is enough space for *Jatropha* cultivation to reach the aim of 11.2 million hectares, which would eventually be enough to replace the Diesel fuel [5]. Vegetable oils offer properties that allow them to be used in diesel engines without requiring any hardware changes. Edible and non-edible vegetable oils are the two types of vegetable oils. Most of these vegetable oil-producing trees are wild and will take care of themselves once established [6,12, 13].

II. PREPARATION OF BIODIESEL

A triglyceride combines Transesterification with an alcohol in the presence of a strong acid or base of vegetable oils, yielding a combination of glycerol and fatty acid alkyl esters. The process for producing biodiesel is as follows: To make methoxide, 6 grams of catalyst are dissolved in 200 ml of methanol. The alkali is then aggressively stirred for 20 minutes in a closed container until it is entirely dissolved. The mixture is then poured into a reactor with moisture-free vegetable oil. At a temperature of 600 to 650, the mixture is stirred for 45 minutes. Methyl alcohol is condensed by placing the condenser on top of the reactor. After that, the condenser is removed, and the surplus methyl alcohol is stirred out for 15 minutes. The mixture became slightly turbid and changed to brown in a few minutes since free glycerol was emulsified and generated throughout the reaction. The mixture is removed and placed in the separating funnel after one hour, and the glycerol component begins to settle to the bottom. In a separating funnel, the mixture was allowed to gravitationally settle overnight. It was found that there had developed two distinct layers, one pale yellow at the top and the other dark brown at the bottom. Glycerol is taken out of the bottom layer without damaging the funnel [7, 8]. Before performance testing, key characteristics of *Pongamia* oil, its methyl ester, and its mixes are identified and tabulated. Table I provides a list of the fuel's characteristics.

TABLE I
PROPERTIES OF BIODIESEL AND ITS BLENDS WITH DIESEL [9, 2007]

Properties	M10	M20	M40	M50	M100	Diesel
Density at40°C	830	835	846	850	871	828
Specific Gravity at40° C	0.831	0.835	0.846	0.851	0.873	0.828
K.V (cst) at 40°C	3.98	4.18	4.49	4.76	5.49	3.8
C.Value (kJ/kg)	42540	42120	41294	40879	38869	42960
Flash Point (°C)	101	102	109	114	178	56
Fire Point (°C)	112	119	123	127	185	63

III. EXPERIMENTATION

The investigation used a Kirloskar Engine test bench, which includes a 4.4 Liter, four-cylinder, four-stroke, 16-valve, in-line, turbocharged, direct injection diesel engine, and dynamometer for loading applications. A computer-assisted experimental engine configuration is shown in Figure 1. A digital meter output inductive pick-up sensor was utilized to monitor and indicate engine speed and an eddy current dynamometer to measure load. AVL smoke meter was used to detect carbon dioxide (CO₂), carbon monoxide (CO), hydrocarbons, nitrous oxide, and oxygen content. Fig. 1 shows air pollution monitoring systems that measured CO₂ and CO. The engine was initially powered by diesel, then methyl esters of oil, and finally a combination of the two. On the engine, several fuel blends and diesel were tested for performance analysis and emissions characteristics. The tests were carried out three times, with the average value being included in the research. Thermal efficiency, braking-specific fuel consumption, smoke density, unburned hydrocarbon, and carbon monoxide were all analyzed using graphs.

Fig. 1 Kirloskar Engine Test Bench

experiments used a 27-minute injection time, a 180-bar injection pressure, a 1500-RPM speed, and a 17.5 compression ratio. The tests were performed on a clean diesel engine under no load, 25% full load, 50% full load, 75% full load, and full load circumstances. Fuel flow, air flow, exhaust smoke opacity, NO_x, CO, CO₂, and unburned hydrocarbon emissions were all recorded at this point. The engine was then operated under the same conditions with straight bio-diesel and blends ranging from 10% to 50% by volume with diesel, with the same performance and emission testing as before.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Biodiesel, diesel, and their mixes were tested in engines at various injection pressures from no load to full load. Under the same operating conditions, the test was also conducted with Diesel as fuel for comparison. In comparison to diesel, Fig. 2 demonstrates the deviation of brake thermal efficiency (BTE) with Brake Power (BP) for methyl ester and its blends. The BTE improves when the BP rises for all fuels. The reason for this is a reduction in heat loss. Fig. 2 indicates that BTE variation at full load, the M10, M20, M30, and M40 fuels are more efficient than diesel, but the M50 and M100 fuels are slightly less efficient. The highest BTE for M20 at full load is 30%, which is more than the maximum BTE for diesel (28%) at full load.

Fig. 2 Variation of Brake Thermal Efficiency with Load

Fig. 3 shows the variation in brake thermal efficiency for various fuel mixes as a function of injection pressure at full load. Vegetable oils atomize properly and are mixed upon injection; all fuels have a low efficiency at lower pressure. When the injection pressure is increased, the BTE rises due to reduced viscosity, enhanced atomization, and improved combustion. At a 200 kPa injection pressure, all fuels tested have the highest efficiency. At 220 kPa pressure, the efficiency decreased because the droplet size decreased, resulting in the injection of a very tiny fuel spray. Fuel sprays are injected and their penetration is measured. As a result, fuel droplet penetration is minimized. At full load conditions, all mixes achieve their optimum efficiency at 200 kPa. The efficiency climbed to 29.15% when the injection pressure was

increased to 200 kPa, demonstrating that the efficiency improved by around 1.5 % with the increase in pressure.

Fig. 3 Influence of Injection Pressure on Brake Thermal Efficiency

Fig. 4 shows for different fuels and blends, the variance of BSFC with varied injection pressure at full load. For all fuels, the BSFC is observed to decrease as injection pressure is increased. This may be a result of increased fuel-air mixing and spray atomization at optimal injection pressure brought on by increased penetration length and spray cone angle with increasing injection pressure. For all fuels tested, the lowest BSFC was determined to be about 210 bar injection pressure.

Fig. 4: Influence of Injection pressure on BSFC

Fig. 4 shows that at 210 bar injection pressure, the BSFC for M20 is 0.310 kg/kWh and M50 fuel is 0.315 kg/kWh, respectively. The BSFC is also lowered when the injection pressure is increased from 160 bars to 210 bars. Fig. 5 compares diesel fuel with Pongamia methyl ester and its mixes to illustrate how the BSFC varies with BP volatility. Because biodiesel has a lower calorific value than diesel, the BSFC for M50 and M100 fuels is greater. M10, M20, M30, and M40 fuels have a substantially lower BSFC than diesel fuel at full load. M20 has a BSFC of 0.289 Kg/kW-hr, whereas diesel has a BSFC of 0.32 Kg/kW-hr.

Fig. 5 Influence of variation of load on NOx

The change of NOx with BP for various fuels is depicted in Fig. 5. The amount of NOx produced by all fuels increases as the load increases. This is because NOx emissions become increasingly temperature-dependent as the temperature of the combustion chamber rises in line with the load. M20 and M40 fuels emit 1030 and 1040 parts per million (ppm) of NOx, respectively at full load conditions, which is lower than diesel.

Fig. 6 Influence of injection pressure on NOx

Fig. 6 depicts the variation in NOx levels as a function of injection pressure for various fuels at full load conditions. It has been observed that as injection pressure is increased, the level of NOx increases. The NOx emissions were lower when comparing the 210-bar injection pressure to the residual pressure. With increased injection pressure, the engine exhaust temperature drops, resulting in decreased NOx emissions. For M20 and M50 fuels, NOx was measured at full load at 170 psi. NOx emissions were decreased to 1050 ppm when the pressure was 210 bars. For all fuels and blends, Figure 7 demonstrates the link between UBHC and BP. For all fuels, the UBHC rises as the load rises. When compared to diesel fuel, biodiesel, and biodiesel blends emit fewer UBHCs. The UBHC of M20 is 30 to 35 percent lower than that of diesel, indicating that the fuel is more thoroughly burnt.

Fig. 7 Influence of variation of load on Hydrocarbon (HC)

HC fluctuates as a function of injection pressure for various fuels as shown in figure 8. HC emissions are higher at a lower injection pressure of 170 bars, according. This is due to the incomplete burning of the fuel at lower injection pressures. The lower HC is measured at 210 bars for all the fuels tested. HC emissions for M20 fuel at 170 bars at full load conditions is 45 ppm. When the injection pressure is increased, HC emissions also increase by 20 ppm

Fig. 8 Influence of variation of Hydrocarbon (HC) concerning injection pressure

V. CONCLUSIONS

Extensive tests were carried out on a four-stroke, one-cylinder, vertical, water-cooled direct-injection diesel engine throughout the current investigation using diesel, Pongamia biodiesel, and biodiesel at different volume ratios. The following conclusions are drawn

- Pongamia oil's kinematic viscosity and specific gravity are lowered during transesterification, while its calorific value is raised.
- The Break Thermal Efficiency for M20 to M40 fuels is higher (for M20 is about 30%), which is around 2% more than diesel and other mixtures.
- Pure biodiesel has a greater BSFC than diesel fuels, while M20 fuel has a lower BSFC than diesel fuels and various blends
- When comparing pure biodiesel to diesel fuel, NO_x emissions are higher for pure biodiesel and lower for M20 fuel.
- Biodiesel and its blends greatly reduce UBHC, CO, and smoke opacity, when compared to all blends, 20 percent methyl esters with diesel fuel have higher performance and lower emission characteristics, according to engine performance and emission tests

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This study was supported by Dr. D. Y. Patil Institute of Technology Pimpri Pune in the frame of the research project for post-graduate study.

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NOMENCLATURE

1. TDC- Top dead center
2. BSFC- Brake-specific fuel consumption
3. SEC -Specific energy consumption
4. BTE -Brake thermal efficiency
5. CO -Carbon monoxide
6. DI -Direct injection
7. UBHC - Unburned hydrocarbon
8. ppm - Parts per million
9. PME - Pongamia oil methyl ester
10. M10- 10%PME and 80% diesel
11. M20 - 20%PME and 80% diesel
12. M40 - 40%PME and 60% diesel
13. M50 - 50%PME and 50% diesel
14. M100-100% PME